

ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE TO SEEDS IN GIN MACHINES

Abdukarimov Tolibkhon Tokhirkhon oglu¹

of Engineering and Technology Direction of technology
of primary processing of natural fibers
Tolibxontolibxon00@gmail.com

Shamshidinov Ibragimkhon Muminkhon oglu²

of Engineering and Technology Direction of technology
of primary processing of natural fibers

Rakhimov Faizullo Khusanboy oglu³

of Engineering and Technology Basic doctoral student
¹⁻²⁻³Namangan Institute

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Annotation. The main content of the article is an analysis of the shortcomings observed in the operation of cotton gins at ginneries. Also mentioned were the problems of separating the fiber from the seed, the effect of the saw on the seed, and the causes of defects.

Keywords: Pipe, cotton, lattice, raw materials, air, mechanization, screw conveyors, elevators, fan, raw material, shop, separator, flow, system, element, extractor.

Introduction. In the world market of textile products, we occupy a high position in the production of cotton fiber. The production uses about 24-25 million tons of cotton fiber, which grows from year to year [1]. We all know that ginning is the main operation of the technological process of primary processing of raw cotton, which is the process of separating cotton fiber from seeds. When cleaning cotton, we use the main building, the main production building. The main production building will house the main workshops for ginning and fiber cleaning, linting, fiber waste processing and preparation (compaction) of finished fiber products [2]. Depending on the type of fiber processing, the gin machine is divided into saw and roller.

One of the main requirements for a saw ginning machine is to obtain a quality product, avoid damage when separating the seeds from the fiber, achieve high machine performance, and ensure the maximum yield of cotton fiber.

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The main working body in saws is a cylinder made of saw blades [3]. In these demons, the grate works together with saw blades to separate the fiber from the

seed. The seed that enters the Gene's working chamber is picked up by the saw teeth, which rotate next to the seed comb, and transferred to the grate. In the working chamber, pieces of cotton attached to the teeth stick together with other pieces of cotton, pull them together and form a raw roller [4]. This roller rotates in the opposite direction of the saw rotation and provides a continuous supply of cotton fiber to the saw teeth.

Damage to the seed, the presence of many defects in the fibrous composition, i.e. a mixture of seed husks, and the appearance of which the saw blade is made very sharp, i.e. the width of the tip of its tooth should be less than 0.4 mm. It is also observed that the troughs come out when mixed with the fiber due to the trough being in the desired position. Scientific and experimental studies have made it possible to determine the optimal basis for the processing of raw cotton, the moisture content of cotton.

They recommended that when cotton was processed with more than 9% moisture, there would be a reduction in cleaning efficiency in the production line, an increase in fiber defects and contamination levels.

May be the cause of the deviation [5]. Another cause of seed damage is an increase in the density of the raw roll due to the pressure of the seed comb. a change is observed. Fibrous output of semen coming out of the jinn machine the reason is that a certain number of saw teeth are broken or the seed comb it became known that the diggers could be injured. Another key One disadvantage is that the seeds are mixed with fiber and husks, this was reflected in the increase in the distance between the columns.

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